

Linear, Radial & Scalar Magnitudes

Agustín A. Tobla

Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 License

(2015) Buenos Aires

Argentina

In classical mechanics, this paper presents the definitions and the relations of the linear, radial and scalar magnitudes of a pair of particles ij .

Introduction

i) The definitions of the linear, radial and scalar magnitudes of a pair of particles ij , where \vec{r}_i and \vec{r}_j are the positions of the particles i and j , are as follows:

§ The linear position \vec{r}_{ij} , the linear velocity \vec{v}_{ij} and the linear acceleration \vec{a}_{ij} , are given by:

$$\vec{r}_{ij} \doteq (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)$$

$$\vec{v}_{ij} \doteq d(\vec{r}_{ij})/dt = (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j)$$

$$\vec{a}_{ij} \doteq d^2(\vec{r}_{ij})/dt^2 = (\vec{a}_i - \vec{a}_j)$$

§ The radial position r_{ij} , the radial velocity \dot{r}_{ij} and the radial acceleration \ddot{r}_{ij} , are given by:

$$r_{ij} \doteq |\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|$$

$$\dot{r}_{ij} \doteq d(r_{ij})/dt = [(\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)] / |\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|$$

$$\ddot{r}_{ij} \doteq d^2(r_{ij})/dt^2 = [(\vec{a}_i - \vec{a}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j) + (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) \cdot (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) - [(\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)]^2 / (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)^2] / |\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|$$

§ The scalar position τ_{ij} , the scalar velocity $\dot{\tau}_{ij}$ and the scalar acceleration $\ddot{\tau}_{ij}$, are given by:

$$\tau_{ij} \doteq 1/2 (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)$$

$$\dot{\tau}_{ij} \doteq d(\tau_{ij})/dt = (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j)$$

$$\ddot{\tau}_{ij} \doteq d^2(\tau_{ij})/dt^2 = (\vec{a}_i - \vec{a}_j) \cdot (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j) + (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j) \cdot (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j)$$

ii) The relations between the linear, radial and scalar magnitudes of a pair of particles ij , they can be obtained from the above definitions, are as follows:

$$\tau_{ij} = 1/2 r_{ij} r_{ij} = 1/2 \vec{r}_{ij} \cdot \vec{r}_{ij}$$

$$\dot{\tau}_{ij} = \dot{r}_{ij} r_{ij} = \vec{v}_{ij} \cdot \vec{r}_{ij}$$

$$\ddot{\tau}_{ij} = \ddot{r}_{ij} r_{ij} + \dot{r}_{ij} \dot{r}_{ij} = \vec{a}_{ij} \cdot \vec{r}_{ij} + \vec{v}_{ij} \cdot \vec{v}_{ij}$$

iii) The magnitudes [\vec{r}_{ij} , r_{ij} , \dot{r}_{ij} , \ddot{r}_{ij} , τ_{ij} , $\dot{\tau}_{ij}$ and $\ddot{\tau}_{ij}$] are invariant under transformations between inertial and non-inertial reference frames.